

MAKING HIV PREVENTION WORK:

How Can Policies be Improved to Support Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) Use & Adherence in sub-Saharan Africa. Policy Brief

Introduction

PrEP stands as a highly effective HIV prevention method, reducing the risk of HIV acquisition by over 90% when taken consistently, but its efficacy is contingent on consistent adherence. While awareness campaigns and policy efforts have successfully increased PrEP uptake, high rates of discontinuation continue to undermine its public health impact. *This highlights why adherence, not just uptake, is critical for PrEP effectiveness.*

In sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), structural inequalities, healthcare resource limitations, and sociocultural dynamics shape PrEP access and use. PrEP's potential is undermined when individuals disengage or do not use it during periods of increased risk. Questions emerge about what strategies have been effective in supporting effective use of PrEP, and what the lessons are for policymakers moving forward.

We conducted a review aimed at identifying effective interventions and implementation strategies that support effective PrEP use and adherence, and to distil lessons for policymakers.

Key Takeaways

- **Integrate Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) services and adherence support into existing national HIV and sexual and reproductive health (SRH) services, such as family planning and antenatal programmes, to avoid stand-alone programmes and strengthen sustainability.**
- **Decentralise PrEP services by expanding PrEP access and use support through community-based sites, drop-in centres, and community health worker-led outreach to reach adolescents and marginalised groups effectively.**
- **Simplify support protocols by adopting a “minimum adherence support package” in national guidelines (e.g., brief counselling, optional SMS reminders, quarterly check-ins).**

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Scope of the review

A variety of intervention packages have been implemented to support PrEP adherence and effective use. We looked at how the interventions address adherence barriers at an individual level, healthcare provider and system level, as well as at a community level.

Figure 1: Number of studies included in the review by country

- **Forty (40) peer-reviewed articles from PubMed (2019-2025) focusing on PrEP adherence and support in 9 South-to-South Learning Network (SSLN) countries** were included in the review, see figure 1 above for distribution.
- Most evidence comes from **Kenya (16 studies)**, **Uganda (15 studies)**, and **South Africa (11 studies)**, with fewer from **Eswatini (1)**, **Malawi (2)**, **Nigeria (1)**, **Tanzania (1)**, **Zambia (2)**, and **Zimbabwe (2)**.

Access more information on the methodology by clicking [here](#). The results are underpinned by a framework that highlights context-specific approaches that address both user needs and health system approaches.

Findings

Overall, more than half of the studies (22 out of 40) reported an improvement in PrEP adherence. Of these, 10 used objective measures such as drug-level testing. Of the studies reviewed, interventions that focused on individual PrEP users were the most tested (14); followed by multi-level interventions (11) and interventions that combined individual level with health care interventions (8), with a smaller number testing other models.

Using the more objective measures, the combination of individual-level and healthcare interventions seems to yield the best PrEP adherence outcomes.

Figure 2 presents the tested adherence intervention types and the number of studies that showed improvements in PrEP adherence outcome by type of measure.

Figure 2: Interventions implemented that successfully increased adherence

Intervention approaches that have worked:

Individual-level Interventions

Individual-level interventions, often combined with healthcare interventions, proved to be most successful in improving PrEP adherence. Successful individual interventions addressed:

- Education on effective use of the PrEP method.
- Personalised counselling.
- Risk assessment guidance.
- Personal readiness to use PrEP counselling.

Click [here](#) for more information on types of successful individual-level interventions.

Healthcare setting interventions

Healthcare interventions were most effective when they:

- Addressed healthcare provider knowledge and bias.
- Broadened the range of providers delivering PrEP.
- Integrated PrEP into existing health services.
- Enabling healthcare providers to adapt service delivery in flexible ways.
- Allow for varied delivery locations and refill options, such as community-based distribution or pharmacies, or differentiated service hours.

*A strong example comes from the **Partners Scale Up Project** in Kenya, which offered daily oral PrEP to women and men aged 18+ and trained health providers in PrEP delivery within 25 high-volume public HIV clinics.*

*This project demonstrated measurable **improvements in PrEP adherence**, assessed through dried blood spot testing and pharmacy refills. Key elements included adding PrEP topics to routine health talks, making follow-up calls to clients who missed appointments, and holding regular staff meetings to troubleshoot PrEP service challenges. Clinics also introduced client-friendly adaptations, such as fast-tracking PrEP users and dispensing PrEP within consultation rooms rather than at separate pharmacies.*

Recommendations for policymakers

As a policymaker and/or Ministry of Health official, consider the following recommendations to reduce implementation barriers, improve service integration, and ensure that PrEP reaches those who need it most:

1 Leverage **existing** platforms and infrastructure

Integrate PrEP services and adherence support into national HIV and SRH services (e.g., Antiretroviral therapy (ART), maternal and child health (MCH), family planning (FP)) rather than stand-alone services.

2 **Decentralised** PrEP Delivery

Expand PrEP access & use support through community-based sites, drop-in centres, and community health worker (CHW)-led outreach to reach underserved communities and marginalised groups effectively.

3 Do **standardise** support

Adopt a “minimum adherence support package” in national guidelines (e.g., brief counselling, optional SMS reminders, quarterly check-ins).

4 Do **expand** PrEP delivery

Expand the range of existing cadres of healthcare providers (e.g., Pharmacists, CHWs) and facilities eligible to deliver PrEP to reduce the need for specialised staff or major new investments.

5 Promote **regional** learning

Use the SSLN or other regional networks to develop technical guidance and share tools and lessons across countries that are further ahead (e.g., Kenya, Uganda) and those with few documented adherence interventions (e.g., Tanzania, Nigeria), reducing duplication and costs.

6 Revising **restrictive** facility policies

That may limit uptake and continuation, such as flexibility in clinic operating hours, removing consent requirements, destigmatization of key populations, etc.

Additional Resources

SSLN and i2i developed a [Standard Operating Procedure for Injectable Lenacapavir as a Pre-exposure Prophylaxis](#) to support the development and adoption of national SOPs that align with World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations and guidance on injectable lenacapavir (LEN) as pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP).

Suggested Citation

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To access more information on the review, see below:

- [Overview Brief](#)
- [Methodology Brief](#)
- [Learning Brief for Programme Implementers](#)
- [Learning Brief for Ministry of Health and National AIDS Commission Officials](#)

The full rapid review slide deck can be accessed [here](#)

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